

TECHNOLOGY OF FREEZE PROCESSING OF GRAPES.

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Annotatsiya: This article provides information on the effect of processing and storage of grapes and the freezing of grapes on the sugar content of wort.

Key words: Bayan shirey, glucose, wine product, sugar content, physical and chemical indicators.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve and develop the grape and wine industry" [1] requires the selection of technical varieties of grapes, the development of varietal viticulture and winemaking, and the expansion of the types of finished products for export.

In recent years, excessive production of wine products has been observed in Uzbekistan. The focus on expanding the cultivation of varietal viticulture requires the search for innovative technologies of grape processing for the production of ready-made products for export. Thus, the microeconomic analysis of the available raw materials showed the need for their rational use for the production of wine, which is in high demand in the world market. Icewine was originally created in the 1700s in the cold climate wine regions of Europe - Germany, Austria and Canada.

The grapes remain on the vine until December and January. Ripe berries are dehydrated by continuous freezing and thawing. The wonderful process of collecting sugars, acids and extracts in the grape berry enhances the flavor. gives a "peacock" taste. Due to the concentration of fruity aromas, ice creams are called "unmatched", real, noble, unique sweet wines.

They usually have 15% actual alcohol but no more than 22%, often 17 to 20%. Fermentation is completely inhibited or stopped when alcohol is added, leaving a lot of sugar.

Naturally, sweet wine usually contains more fructose than glucose. The fermentation process can explain this relationship: almost all wine yeasts are glucophilic, meaning they ferment glucose faster than fructose, the unfermented sugar being mostly fructose.

The grapes were left on the vine until December, when they were artificially cryoextracted at -8°C . [3] Only the sweetest juice was pressed in the basket presses when the grapes were frozen (first pressing), and the pressing stopped when the juice began to thin. The sugar content of the grapes does not affect the

sugar content of the wort after cryoextraction, but the temperature at which the grapes are harvested and pressed has a significant effect, which actually determines the sugar content of the juice. Grape juice contains water (70-80%), sugar (18-24%). The sugar is dissolved and lowers the freezing point of the juice in the grapes, so it does not freeze until the temperature reaches -7°C or -8°C.

Experimental options for obtaining grape juice after low-temperature processing are presented for coding:

Option 1 - "Bayan Shirey" grapes should be used without low temperature treatment;

Option 2 - Bayan Shirey grapes should be processed at a low temperature;

All variants of the samples were analyzed and the main parameters of the wort: sugar content was determined by direct titration; titratable acidity - with an indicator, volatile acidity - by distillation. [Gerzhikov] manuals], sugar was determined on Fgilent 1100 Degasser G1379A Quat Pump G1311 liquid chromatograph. ALS G1313A Colcom G1316A. RID G1362 A Agilent ChemStation Rev / B / 01/03 SupelcosilitC-NH2 5 micron 4.6 250 mm "Supelco", USA. "VWR. Poland. Biohit. Finland. AnD GR-202. "AnD" Japan. Millipore Simplicity "Millipore" France S 30 H

Table 1 shows the results of the analysis of samples of Bayan-shirei variety

Physical and chemical parameters of the surface

№ п/п	samples	indicators		
		Sugar content,%	Titratable acid, g / dm ³	The composition of the pilot
1	Option 1	25,5	3,6	0,1
2	Option 2	31,9	3,6	0,1

As can be seen from the data in the table, the sugar content of "Bayan-shirey" increased by 17%, while titratable and volatile acids remained unchanged.

The analysis of these data shows deep hydrolytic processes of polysaccharides and other components of wort, whose half-life or hydrolysis products are mono- and oligosaccharides.

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